

Acceptability of Human Papillomavirus Vaccine by the Population of Two Health Districts in Yaounde-Cameroon

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Abstract

Human papillomavirus (HPV) infections with high oncogenic risk are responsible for 7.7% of cancers (mainly cervical cancer) in developing countries. Vaccination is considered to be one of the greatest public health successes, but despite its proven effectiveness, vaccination does not longer enjoy popular support, which leads to a coverage in terms of HPV vaccine almost non-existent. A descriptive and analytical cross-sectional study was conducted in the health districts of Nkolndongo and Djoungolo, with the aim of analyzing the acceptability of Human Papillomavirus vaccine in these health districts. From a structured questionnaire administered to 330 parents and 32 Community health Workers (CHWs), we found an insufficient 33.6% moderate level of HPV vaccine acceptability, a statistical significant association between parents' marital status and HPV vaccine acceptability (OR = 0.369; P value = 0.027; 95%; CI = [0.153, 0.890]), a statistically significant association between knowing someone with cervical cancer and accepting her child to get vaccinated against HPV (OR =0.409; P-value = 0.006; 95%; CI= [0.217; 0.769]), a statistically significant association between accepting HPV vaccine and agreeing to have her child vaccinated against HPV at 51.6%, and a statistically significant association between knowing that HPV vaccine was available in health facilities and its acceptability (OR=0.210; P-value = 0.021; 95%; CI = [0.056; 0.793]). To expand HPV vaccination coverage, various activities should be carried out among the population to improve their knowledge about cervical cancer and the availability of HPV vaccine. The focus should be on unmarried parents and parents engaged in a free union relationship. Health workers should use true life stories about cervical cancer as a means of raising awareness and the list of health facilities administrating HPV vaccine should be made known to the population.

Introduction

Cervical cancer is a global phenomenon estimated in 2018 at around 570,000 new cases resulting in around 311,000 (54.6%) deaths during the same year [1]. Vaccination is considered as one of the greatest public health successes, but despite its proven effectiveness, vaccination no longer enjoys popular support, which leads to a coverage in terms of HPV vaccine almost non-

existent. Facing this problem, we asked ourselves the following question: what is the level of acceptability of Human Papillomavirus vaccine for the population of the Health Districts of Nkolndongo and Djoungolo? This research question guided our study on the problem of non-existence coverage of HPV vaccination. In this study, we proposed to analyze the acceptability of Human Papillomavirus vaccine by the population of two

More Information

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Health Districts in Yaounde-Cameroon. More specifically, we measured the level of acceptability of Human Papillomavirus vaccine. Added to it, we identified the socio-demographic characteristics of households associated with HPV vaccine acceptability. And finally, we examined the influence of perceptions, attitudes and practices on HPV vaccine acceptability. Using the theory of planned behavior combined to the Health Belief Model to interpret our results, information that resulted made it possible to develop strategies related to the increase in coverage of HPV vaccination.

Materials and Methods

We conducted a cross-sectional quantitative prospective study with a descriptive and analytical design in the health districts of Nkolndongo and Djoungolo in Yaounde-Cameroon. The target population consisted of community health workers (CHWs) and any parent of a female child aged 9 to 13 who agreed to participate to the study. In our study, we opted for a two-stage probabilistic cluster sampling method. Two different structured questionnaires were

administered to parents of girls aged 9 to 13 and to community health workers. These tools allowed us to highlight perceptions/knowledge, attitudes and practices related to the acceptability of the HPV vaccine.

We used univariate analysis as a method of analysis, which identified variables with low response rates, null variables, and outliers. A bivariate analysis which called in our study a Chi square test was used to identify dependent variables. Finally, a multinomial logistic regression was performed to eliminate confounders and make adjustment. Each test was significant at a 5% P-value threshold.

Results

Level of acceptability of Human Papillomavirus vaccine

The 330 parents who participated to our study were distributed as follows: 294 women and 36 men. Our results showed a moderate level of HPV vaccine acceptability of 33.6% in both sexes as shown in the table below:

Table 1: level of HPV vaccine acceptability among parents

			Gender		
			Men	Women	Total
HPV Vaccine Acceptability	Undecided	n	5	49	54
		%	13.9%	16.7%	16.4%
	Against	n	21	144	165
		%	58.3%	49.0%	50.0%
	For	n	10	101	111
		%	27.8%	34.4%	33.6%
Total		n	36	294	330
		%	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%

On the other hand, among the 32 CHWs enrolled in our study, 68.8% were willing to support HPV vaccine whereas others were either against (15.6%) or undecided (15.6%).

Association of HPV Vaccine Acceptability and Sociodemographic Characteristics

With parents

Parents' age (p-value = 0.21) as well as gender (P-value = 0.74), parents' region of origin (P-value = 0.75), religion (P-value = 0.55), and Parents' education level (P-value = 0.33) were not significantly associated with HPV vaccine acceptability.

Although parents education level was not significantly associated with the acceptability of HPV vaccine (P-value = 0.33), parents with a higher level of education (Secondary school and University: 36.2%) better accepted HPV vaccination compared to parents with a lower level of education (Illiterate and Primary school: 27.4%). Parents with a secondary education level (36.9%) best accepted HPV vaccine compared to

parents of other levels of education (Illiterate: 32.0%, Primary school: 25.7%, and University: 33.9%).

Regarding religion, parents of other religions (60%) accepted HPV vaccination the most compared to Muslims (50%) and Christians (32.8%). The difference between the three groups was not statistically significant at 5% threshold (P-value = 0.062).

Marital status (OR = 0.369; P value = 0.027; 95%; CI = [0.153, 0.890]) was statistically significantly associated with HPV vaccine acceptability at 7%. The odd of being married was an advantage for HPV vaccine acceptability. However, those who were only in a free union relationship were 63.1% more likely to be undecided regarding the acceptability of the HPV vaccine.

Among CHWs

A total of 32 community health workers (CHWs) were interviewed in Djoungolo and Nkolndongo health districts.

Regarding their individual characteristics, it appeared that their age group (P-value =0.21), gender (P-value = 0.45), region of origin (P-value = 0.65), religion (P-value = 0.79), marital status (P-value = 0.84), and education level (P-value =0.061) had no statistical significant influence on HPV vaccine acceptability.

There was no statistical difference between the behavior of CHWs with a lower level of education (illiterates and those of primary school education level) and CHWs with a higher education level (Those of secondary education and university) towards their willingness to support HPV vaccine.

Associations of HPV Vaccine Acceptability and Perceptions/Knowledge, Attitudes and Practices With parents

1. Parents’ perceptions/knowledge of cervical cancer and HPV vaccine acceptability

The level of parents’ knowledge about cervical cancer showed that being aware of cervical cancer (P-value = 0.6) was not associated with HPV vaccine acceptability. Similarly, HPV vaccine acceptability was not associated with the odd of knowing the type of person targeted by cervical cancer (P-value = 0.2), the odd of knowing the causing virus of cervical cancer (P-value = 0.3), the odd of knowing the means of transmission of cervical cancer (P-value = 0.3), being aware of cervical vaccine (P-value = 0.3) and the odd of knowing the type of person eligible for cervical vaccine (P-value = 0.10).

2. Attitudes of parents on cervical cancer and acceptability of HPV vaccination

Among parents, there was a statistically significant association between knowing someone with cervical cancer and accepting her child to get vaccinated against HPV (OR =0.409; P-value = 0.006; 95%; CI= [0.217; 0.769]). Therefore, parents who knew someone with

cervical cancer had 59.1% more chance to accept their children to get vaccinated against HPV. In fact, according to table 2, parents who have never known anyone with cervical cancer were the least accepting to have their children vaccinated against HPV. Indeed, only 24% of parents who have never known any person with cervical cancer accepted to permit their children to get vaccinated against HPV whereas this proportion was almost doubled among parents who have known people with cervical cancer. In fact, there were 44% of parents who have known someone with cervical cancer accepting their children to get vaccinated against HPV. In addition, it also appeared among parent a statistically significant association between accepting HPV vaccine and agreeing to have her child vaccinated against HPV at 51.6%. Indeed, those who refused to have their children get vaccinated against HPV had 95.4% more chance to be undecided concerning HPV vaccine acceptability (OR =0.046; P-value = 0.000; 95%; CI= [0.018; 0.119]) and an increased chance of 99.5% to reject HPV vaccine (OR =0.005; P-value = 0.000; 95%; CI= [0.001; 0.019]). Indeed, parents accepting HPV vaccination would agree to have their children vaccinated against HPV. We noted that 73% of parents who accepted HPV vaccination agreed to have their children vaccinated against HPV, whereas almost all the parents (1.2%) who rejected HPV vaccination refused to have their children vaccinated against HPV. About their motivation, it appeared that it had a significant effect on HPV vaccine acceptability. We noted that 47% of parents whose motivation was to respect doctor's recommendations accepted HPV vaccination. Moreover, 98.9% of parents who had no motivation had no intention to get their child vaccinated against HPV.

Table 2: Attitudes about cervical cancer and HPV vaccine acceptability

Characteristic	Would you agree to have your child vaccinated against cervical cancer ?			P-value
	No (241)	Yes (89)	Total (330)	
Do you know anyone with cervical cancer ?				0.006
No	214 (76%)	68 (24%)	282 (100%)	
Yes	27 (56%)	21 (44%)	48 (100%)	
Are you favorable for vaccination against cervical cancer due to HPV infection on girls aged 9 to 13?				0.000
Yes	30 (27%)	81 (73%)	111 (100%)	
No	163 (99%)	2 (1.2%)	165 (100%)	
No idea	48 (89%)	6 (11%)	54 (100%)	

3. Vaccination practices and HPV vaccine acceptability among parents

We found a statistically significant association between knowing that HPV vaccine was available in health facilities and its acceptability (OR=0.210; P-value = 0.021; 95%; CI = [0.056; 0.793]). So, parents who did not

know that the vaccine against cervical cancer due to HPV infection was available in health facilities had an increase chance of 79% to reject HPV vaccine. In fact, more parents [60% (9/15)] who knew that HPV vaccine was available in health facilities were willing to have their children vaccinated.

Table 3: Vaccination practices and HPV vaccine acceptability among parents

Characteristic	Do you know that HPV vaccine is available in health facilities?			P-value
	No (315)	Yes (15)	Total (330)	
Are you favorable for vaccination against cervical cancer due to HPV infection on girls aged 9 to 13?				0.021
Yes	102 (92%)	9 (8%)	111 (100%)	
No	162 (98%)	3 (2%)	165 (100%)	
No idea	51 (94%)	3 (6%)	54 (100%)	

Among CHWs

1. CHWs perceptions / knowledge of cervical cancer and HPV vaccine acceptability
Regarding knowledge of cervical cancer and the HPV vaccine among CHWs, it appeared that all CHWs have

already heard of cervical cancer (100%). We also noted that 96.9% of them were ignorant of how the disease is transmitted. Regarding the vaccine against cervical cancer, we found that 84.4% of CHWs had already heard of the vaccine.

Table 4: Knowledge of CHWs on cervical cancer

Characteristic	N = 32
Have you ever heard of cervical cancer?	
Yes	32 (100%)
How is cervical cancer virus transmitted?	
sexual activity	1 (3.1%)
No idea	31 (96.9%)
Have you ever heard of the vaccine against cervical cancer due to Human Papillomavirus infection?	
No	5 (15.6%)
Yes	27 (84.4%)

Finally among CHWs, there was no statistically significant association between being aware of cervical cancer; the odd of knowing the means of transmission of cervical cancer (P value = 0.143), the odd of being aware of HPV vaccine (P value = 0.175) and CHWs support for HPV vaccine.

2. Attitudes and practices of CHWs on cervical cancer and acceptability of vaccination

We recorded 68.8% of CHWs willing to support HPV vaccine, while 15.6% were against HPV vaccine and 15.6% of them expressed no opinion. Similarly, 96.9% of CHWs have not received any training to carry out specific activities on HPV vaccination as shown in the table below. However, there was no statistical significant association between being trained and the will to support HPV vaccine among CHWs (P value = 0.683).

Table 5: CHW attitudes and practices regarding HPV vaccine

Characteristic	N = 32
Are you willing to support the Gardasil vaccination against cervical cancer for girls aged 9 to 13?	
For vaccination	22 (68.8%)
Against vaccination	5 (15.6%)
No idea	5 (15.6%) ¹
Have you received training for activities specific to cervical cancer vaccination?	
No	31 (96.9%)
Yes	1 (3,1%)

Discussion

Measuring the level of HPV vaccine acceptability

The 330 parents who participated to our study were distributed as follows: 294 women and 36 men. Our results showed a moderate level of HPV vaccine acceptability of 33.6% in both sexes which was still far below the expected sufficient 80-100% threshold.

We therefore concluded that there was an insufficient level of acceptance of HPV vaccine among the people of these two health districts in Yaounde-Cameroon. These results revealed that people in these two health districts did not believe in the severity of cervical cancer and also in the effectiveness of HPV vaccine. This way of belief can be explained by the fear of becoming barren after having taken HPV vaccine as mentioned in rumors.

Finally, many parents agreed of not being well informed. This ignorance of cervical cancer and its vaccine was observable in comments made by parents who rejected or hesitated to express their acceptance for HPV vaccine.

However, while looking into two components of the Health Belief Model: the "Perceived Threat" and the "Perceived Benefits", we clearly noticed they played an important role in parents' final decision leading to the acceptance of HPV vaccine. In fact, in this study, close to 315 parents (93%) had heard of cervical cancer (Perceived Threat) but only 15 (4.5%) parents were aware of the availability of its vaccine in health facilities (Perceived Benefits) and among these 15 parents, 8 (53%) agreed to have their children vaccinated.

In the Health Belief Model, the "cues to action" component, such as recommendations from doctors, communications or vaccination campaigns influence the perception of the threat of disease[2]. Health actors should therefore implement these various activities to improve the knowledge of cervical cancer (the Perceived threat) and the knowledge of HPV vaccine availability (the Perceived Benefits) to improve HPV vaccination coverage.

On the other hand, among the 32 CHWs enrolled in our study, 68.8% were willing to support HPV vaccine whereas others were either against (15.6%) or undecided (15.6%). As revealed by our study, not all community health workers are willing to engage in supporting HPV vaccine. This lukewarmness towards HPV vaccine observed among community health workers can be explained by the young age of HPV vaccine in Cameroon which was only introduced in November 2020 [3].

Our result on the level of acceptability of HPV vaccine opposes the findings of Brewer & Fazekas (2007) where in a study carried out in the USA on the Predictors of HPV vaccine acceptability, they presented a high acceptability of HPV vaccine. Moreover in this study

based on the Health Believe Model (HBM); people felt vulnerable to the risk of HPV infection. Also, they believed in the effectiveness of the vaccine. And finally, the severity of HPV and cervical cancer was perceived as high.

Association of parents' marital status with HPV vaccine acceptability

Our analyses showed that there was a statistical significant association between parents' marital status and HPV vaccine acceptability (OR = 0.369; P value = 0.027; 95%; CI = [0.153, 0.890]) at 7%. The odd of being married was an advantage for HPV vaccine acceptability. However, those who were only in a free union relationship were 63.1% more likely to be undecided regarding the acceptability of the HPV vaccine. This difference in people behavior towards HPV vaccine acceptability according to their marital status can be explained by our African culture.

In fact, we tend to believe that children are the cement of a relationship. So, protecting a relationship means to protect our children. For this reason, married people will be more likely to adhere to protective measure for their children in order to do good impression on the eye of their partner and ensure their couple survives better. These findings showing that the behavior of people towards HPV vaccine acceptability differs according to their marital status oppose Hanley et al. (2014) [5] results. In fact, in a study carried out in three Japanese cities among 27 fathers (16 single; 11 married), they presented a high level of HPV vaccine acceptability which did not differ by marital status. This divergence of results can be explained by the fact that only people of one sex participated in Hanley et al. (2014) [5] study. The Health Belief Model teaches us according to Rosenstock et al. (1994) [6] that the first two components, namely "Perceived Threat" and "Perceived Benefits", are at the origin of action while the last two components, namely "Other Variables" and "Self-Efficacy", trace a path to action. Therefore, in our study, for the dimension of other variables, marital status stands as a social variable which have influenced parents' perception to pave their way towards a decision regarding HPV vaccine acceptability.

Non association of other Sociodemographic Characteristics with HPV vaccine acceptability

Among parents, no statistical significant association was found between HPV vaccine acceptability and their age (p-value = 0.21) as well as their gender (P-value = 0.74), their region of origin (P-value = 0.75), their religion (P-value = 0.55), and their education level (P-value = 0.33).

In our study, the age of parents ranged from 19 to 94 years with 47.9% being between 19 to 34 years, 41.5% between 35 to 50 years and 10.6% being over 50 years old. However, acceptability of HPV vaccine was

statistically indifferent in these three social classes of created around parents' age (p -value = 0.21).

Among parents, there were 10.9% of men and 89.1% of women. However, the behavior of men towards accepting HPV vaccine showed no statistical difference compared to women (P -value = 0.74).

Regarding religion, parents of other religions (60%) accepted HPV vaccine the most compared to Muslims (50%) and Christians (32.8%). The difference between the three groups was not statistically significant at 5% threshold (P -value = 0.062).

Although parents education level was not significantly associated with the acceptability of HPV vaccine (P -value = 0.33), parents with a higher level of education (Secondary school and University: 36.2%) better accepted HPV vaccine compared to parents with a lower level of education (Illiterate and Primary school: 27.4%). Parents with a secondary education level (36.9%) best accepted HPV vaccine compared to parents of other levels of education (Illiterate: 32.0%, Primary school: 25.7%, and University: 33.9%).

A non-association of parents' age, gender, region of origin, religion, and education level with HPV vaccine acceptability showed how a message can have an impact on the society regardless the age, the gender, the region of origin, the religion and the education level of individuals. This message was indeed underlined by our investigators who noticed that parents were afraid of HPV vaccine because they thought it would cause barrenness in their children.

These results are different from those found by Marlow et al. (2009) [7] through a cross-sectional study of ethnic differences in human papillomavirus awareness and HPV vaccine acceptability that aimed to assess HPV awareness and vaccine acceptability. In a sample of women representing the major ethnic minority groups in the UK, Marlow et al. (2009) [7] revealed that ethnicity and religion was strongly associated with the acceptability of HPV vaccine. In fact, in this study, women from non-Christian religions accepted less HPV vaccine (17-34%).

Similarly, the most common barriers to HPV vaccine in both studies remained the lack of genuine information. On the same line, our results showed that among CHWs, their age group (P -value = 0.21), gender (P -value = 0.45), region of origin (P -value = 0.65), religion (P -value = 0.79), marital status (P -value = 0.84), and education level (P -value = 0.061) had no statistical significant influence on HPV vaccine acceptability.

The age of CHWs involved in our study ranged from 22 to 63 years with 53.1% being between 22 to 34 years, 34.4% between 35 to 50 years and 12.5% being over 50 years old. The difference between these age groups was not statistically significant at 5% threshold (P -value = 0.21).

Among CHWs, there were 56.2% of men and 43.8% of women. Nevertheless, the behavior of men towards supporting HPV vaccine was no statistically difference from those of women (P -value = 0.45).

For CHWs religion, we had 3.1% of Muslims and 96.9% of Christians. The difference between the two groups was not statistically significant at 5% threshold (P -value = 0.79).

Concerning marital status, 62.5% were singles, 3.1% were widows or widowers, 9.4% were engaged in a free union relationship and 25% were married. However, it made no difference in having support from CHWs men regarding HPV vaccine compared to women (P -value = 0.84).

Moreover our results showed that there was no statistical difference between the behavior of CHWs with a lower level of education (illiterates and those of primary school education level: 6.2%) and CHWs with a higher education level (Those of secondary education and university: 93.8%) towards their willingness to support HPV vaccine.

A non-association of CHWs' age, gender, region of origin, religion, marital status, and education level with HPV vaccine acceptability revealed that the support of CHWs to HPV vaccine did not depend on their socio-demographic characteristics.

Non-association of knowledge of cervical cancer and HPV vaccine acceptability

The level of parent's knowledge about cervical cancer showed that being aware of cervical cancer (P -value = 0.6) was not associated with HPV vaccine acceptability. In fact, among parents, most participants seemed to know about cervical cancer but not about HPV vaccine. For instance, we recorded 92.1% of parents being aware of cervical cancer whereas only 37.3% of parents were aware of HPV vaccine.

It therefore appeared that there was a gap in HPV vaccine awareness compared to cervical cancer awareness, which could explain the non-association between parents being aware of cervical cancer and HPV vaccine acceptability (P -value = 0.6). In fact, according to the theory of planned behavior, intention is the predictor of behavior. If parents were only conscious of cervical cancer and not of HPV vaccine, there was no chance that HPV vaccine acceptability could depend on the odd of being aware of cervical cancer.

Similarly, HPV vaccine acceptability was not associated with the odd of knowing the type of person targeted by cervical cancer (P -value = 0.2), the odd of knowing the causing virus of cervical cancer (P -value = 0.3), the odd of knowing the means of transmission of cervical cancer (P -value = 0.3), being aware of cervical vaccine (P -value = 0.3) and the odd of knowing the type of person eligible for cervical vaccine (P -value = 0.10).

Finally, parents' knowledge of cervical cancer was not associated with HPV vaccine acceptability which revealed that accepting HPV vaccine did not depend on what parents knew about cervical cancer.

These results are consistent with those found by Dempsey et al. (2006) [8] who worked on Factors associated with parental acceptance of human papillomavirus vaccines. This study showed that parents who received the HPV information sheet had higher mean scores on the HPV Knowledge Assessment Tool than the control group. However, despite this apparent improvement in knowledge, there was no difference in HPV vaccine acceptability between the 2 groups.

Regarding knowledge of cervical cancer and the HPV vaccine among CHWs, it appeared that there was no statistically significant association between being aware of cervical cancer; the odd of knowing the means of transmission of cervical cancer (P value = 0.143), the odd of being aware of HPV vaccine (P value = 0.175) and CHWs support for HPV vaccine.

In fact, all CHWs have already heard of cervical cancer (100%), which made this variable constant and therefore removed it from the list of factors that could influence CHWs support for HPV vaccine. Thus, CHWs' support for HPV vaccine did not depend on their awareness of cervical cancer.

We also noted that 96.9% of CHWs were ignorant of how cervical cancer virus transmitted. However, CHWs' behavior towards supporting HPV vaccine was not statistically associated with their knowledge on the means of transmission of cervical cancer (P value = 0.143).

Regarding the vaccine against cervical cancer, we found that 84.4% of CHWs had already heard of it. Nevertheless, concerning their support to HPV vaccine, there was no statistical significant difference between those who were aware of cervical cancer vaccine and those who were not aware of it (P value = 0.175).

According to the Health Belief Model, to trigger an action, factors are needed which Rosenstock et al. (1994) [6] call "Cues to Action". These factors can be internal (pain, symptoms) or external (information, event). Regarding our study, this was about the information individuals have about cervical cancer and its vaccine. However, in this study, knowledge of cervical cancer was not established as a "cue to action" for HPV vaccine acceptability since no association was found between the two.

Association between knowing someone with cervical cancer and accepting her child to get vaccinated against HPV

Among parents, there was a statistically significant association between knowing someone with cervical cancer and accepting her child to get vaccinated against HPV (OR =0.409; P-value = 0.006; 95%; CI= [0.217;

0.769]). Therefore, parents who knew someone with cervical cancer had 59.1% more chance to accept their children to get vaccinated against HPV. In fact, according to table 2, parents who have never known anyone with cervical cancer were the least accepting to have their children vaccinated against HPV.

Indeed, only 24% of parents who have never known any person with cervical cancer accepted to permit their children to get vaccinated against HPV whereas this proportion was almost doubled among parents who have known people with cervical cancer. In fact, there were 44% of parents who have known someone with cervical cancer accepting their children to get vaccinated against HPV.

This result on the association between knowing someone with cervical cancer and accepting her child to get vaccinated against HPV aligned with Watson-Jones et al. (2012) [9] findings who have proven in a case-control study entitled "Reasons for Receiving or Not Receiving HPV Vaccination in Primary Schoolgirls in Tanzania" that not knowing anyone who had cancer was one of the factors associated with not receiving the vaccine.

Following the health belief model, the intention to engage in healthy behavior depends on the "perceived susceptibility" and "perceived severity" of an illness. The fact that knowing someone with cervical cancer was associated with accepting her child to get vaccinated against cervical cancer in our study revealed that knowing someone with cervical cancer is an evidence of the reality of the disease, thus satisfying the "perceived susceptibility" condition. Imagining the pain, or even the adverse outcome of the disease on this known person, satisfies the condition of "perceived severity". We could therefore conclude that telling true life stories about cervical cancer to the population could be the best way to increase HPV vaccination coverage.

Association between accepting HPV vaccine and agreeing to have her child vaccinated against HPV

Among parents, there was a statistically significant association between accepting HPV vaccine and agreeing to have her child vaccinated against HPV at 51.6%. Indeed, those who refused to have their children get vaccinated against HPV had 95.4% more chance to be undecided concerning HPV vaccine acceptability (OR =0.046; P-value = 0.000; 95%; CI= [0.018; 0.119]) and an increased chance of 99.5% to reject HPV vaccine (OR =0.005; P-value = 0.000; 95%; CI= [0.001; 0.019]). Indeed, parents accepting HPV vaccination would agree to have their children vaccinated against HPV. We noted that 73% of parents who accepted HPV vaccination agreed to have their children vaccinated against HPV, whereas almost all the parents (1.2%) who rejected HPV vaccination refused to have their children vaccinated against HPV. About their

motivation, it appeared that it had a significant effect on HPV vaccine acceptability. We noted that 47% of parents whose motivation was to respect doctor's recommendations accepted HPV vaccination. Moreover, 98.9% of parents who had no motivation had no intention to get their child vaccinated against HPV.

This result reveals that for parents, accepting HPV vaccine means systematically accepting their children to be vaccinated against HPV. We can therefore conclude that these two intentions are linked as disclosed by Slomovitz et al. (2006) [10] when giving an answer to the question "are women ready to receive the HPV vaccine?", they found that 67% of women with a daughter (n = 156) and 66% of women with a son (n = 137) would consent to their child being vaccinated.

Association between knowing that HPV vaccine was available in health facilities and its acceptability among parents

Our results showed a statistically significant association between knowing that HPV vaccine was available in health facilities and its acceptability (OR=0.210; P-value = 0.021; 95%; CI = [0.056; 0.793]).

So, parents who did not know that the vaccine against cervical cancer due to HPV infection was available in health facilities had an increase chance of 79% to reject HPV vaccine. In fact, more parents [60% (9/15)] who knew that HPV vaccine was available in health facilities were willing to have their children vaccinated.

Behavioral theory has been widely applied in a series of studies on HPV vaccine [11]. Gerend & Shepherd (2012) [12] confirmed that attitude, subjective norms, and self-efficacy are positively correlated with intention to get vaccinated against HPV (r=0.09; r=0.36; r=0.48 respectively) and intention in return is strongly correlated (r=0.62) with behavior. At the same time, Bennett et al. (2012) [13] demonstrated a stronger effect of attitude on the intention to get vaccinated against HPV. Krawczyk et al. (2012) [14] confirmed the results of Bennett and his collaborators according to which a positive attitude is a determining factor in decision-making.

Indeed, vaccination as a means of prevention is well integrated into daily life, and for most of parents, the word "vaccination" represents an image closely linked to the protection against diseases. However, parents mentioned "HPV vaccine process" for children as something "rare". Knowing that HPV vaccine was available in health facilities created some security in parents' mind. They could therefore identify themselves with an institution offering HPV vaccine. They had a reference where if an adverse post-humanization manifestation occurred; they could go there. This safety in mind created a positive attitude that motivated parents to adhere to HPV vaccine.

Based on the Health Belief Model in general and in particular due to the cues to action component ("if vaccine is available in health facilities, i will get vaccinated against HPV") and by combining the theory of planned behavior for the perception of control ("it's me who decides whether to get my child vaccinated or not"), it appears that the intention to get someone's child vaccinated depends on those two variables (Knowing someone with cervical cancer and knowing HPV vaccine is available in health facilities) which allow parents to accept HPV vaccine or not.

We therefore concluded based on the association between knowing that HPV vaccine was available in health facilities and its acceptability that, to expand HPV vaccination coverage, popular and strategic health facilities should be chosen as key reference points for vaccine distribution.

Non-association between being trained and the will to support HPV vaccine among CHWs

In our analysis, there was not a statistical significant association between being trained and the willingness to support HPV vaccine among CHWs (P value = 0.683). We recorded 68.8% of CHWs willing to support HPV vaccine, while 15.6% were against HPV vaccine and 15.6% of them expressed no opinion. Similarly, 96.9% of CHWs have not received any training to carry out specific activities on HPV vaccination. However, the odd of not having been trained influence the quality and relevance of the awareness messages they could offer to the community.

In the combined model of the Health Belief Model and the theory of planned behavior, all the components fall on the intention. Meanwhile training brings forth intentions that favor HPV vaccine and positively influence the community.

In view of what emerges from our analysis, the CHWs who participated in our study did not yet meet the conditions mentioned above. In addition, because HPV vaccine targets a narrow population (girls aged 9–13 years), the development of an effective training program for health workers is essential to successfully guarantee an increase in coverage of HPV vaccination.

Conclusion

Our study aimed at analyzing the acceptability of HPV vaccine in two health districts of Yaounde-Cameroon. To achieve this objective, we carried out a cross-sectional study with a descriptive and analytical design in a quantitative approach. This approach involved administering a structured questionnaire to 330 parents of girls aged 9–13 and 32 community health workers (CHWs).

The theory of planned behavior combined to the Health Belief Model was used to explain our results while measuring the level of acceptability of Human Papillomavirus vaccine. Added to it, we identified the socio-demographic characteristics of households

associated with HPV vaccine acceptability. And finally, we examined the influence of perceptions, attitudes and practices on HPV vaccine acceptability.

Upon measuring the level of acceptability of Human Papillomavirus vaccine, our results showed an insufficient 33.6% moderate level of HPV vaccine acceptability which was still far below the expected sufficient 80-100% threshold. These results revealed that people in these two health districts did not believe in the severity of cervical cancer and also in the effectiveness of HPV vaccine. This way of belief can be explained by the fear of becoming barren after having taken HPV vaccine as mentioned in rumors.

However, while looking into two components of the Health Belief Model: the "Perceived Threat" and the "Perceived Benefits", we clearly noticed they played an important role in parents' final decision leading to the acceptance of HPV vaccine. In fact, in this study, close to 315 parents (93%) had heard of cervical cancer (Perceived Threat) but only 15 (4.5%) parents were aware of the availability of its vaccine in health facilities (Perceived Benefits) and among these 15 parents, 8 (53%) agreed to have their children vaccinated. Health actors should therefore implement various activities to improve the knowledge of cervical cancer (the Perceived threat) and the knowledge of HPV vaccine availability (the Perceived Benefits) to improve HPV vaccination coverage.

While identifying the socio-demographic characteristics of households associated with HPV vaccine acceptability, our analyses showed that there was a statistical significant association between parents' marital status and HPV vaccine acceptability (OR = 0.369; P value = 0.027; 95%; CI = [0.153, 0.890]) at 7%. The odd of being married was an advantage for HPV vaccine acceptability. However, those who were only in a free union relationship were 63.1% more likely to be undecided regarding the acceptability of the HPV vaccine. This difference in people behavior towards HPV vaccine acceptability according to their marital status can be explained by our African culture.

In this study, at the fifth component of the Health belief Model, at the dimension of other variables, marital status stands as a social variable which have influenced parents' perception to pave their way towards a decision regarding HPV vaccine acceptability. On the contrary, no statistical significant association was found between HPV vaccine acceptability and parents' age (p-value = 0.21) as well as their gender (P-value = 0.74), their region of origin (P-value = 0.75), their religion (P-value = 0.55), and their education level (P-value = 0.33). For examining the influence of perceptions, attitudes and practices on HPV vaccine acceptability, there was a statistically significant association between knowing someone with cervical cancer and accepting her child to get vaccinated against HPV (OR =0.409; P-value =

0.006; 95%; CI= [0.217; 0.769]). Therefore, parents who knew someone with cervical cancer had 59.1% more chance to accept their children to get vaccinated against HPV. We could therefore conclude that telling true life stories about cervical cancer to the population could be the best way to increase HPV vaccination coverage.

In addition, there was a statistically significant association between accepting HPV vaccine and agreeing to have her child vaccinated against HPV at 51.6%. Indeed, those who refused to have their children get vaccinated against HPV had 95.4% more chance to be undecided concerning HPV vaccine acceptability (OR =0.046; P-value = 0.000; 95%; CI= [0.018; 0.119]) and an increased chance of 99.5% to reject HPV vaccine (OR =0.005; P-value = 0.000; 95%; CI= [0.001; 0.019]). Our results showed a statistically significant association between knowing that HPV vaccine was available in health facilities and its acceptability (OR=0.210; P-value = 0.021; 95%; CI = [0.056; 0.793]). Parents who did not know that the vaccine against cervical cancer due to HPV infection was available in health facilities had an increase chance of 79% to reject HPV vaccine. Therefore, choosing popular and strategic health facilities as key reference points for vaccine distribution might help improving HPV vaccination coverage.

To expand HPV vaccination coverage, various activities should be carried out among the population to improve their knowledge about cervical cancer and the availability of HPV vaccine. The focus should be on unmarried parents and parents engaged in a free union relationship. Health workers should use true life stories about cervical cancer as a means of raising awareness and the list of health facilities administrating HPV vaccine should be made known to the population.

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Conflict of Interests

Authors declare no conflict of interest.

References

- [1] Arbyn M, Weiderpass E, Bruni L, de Sanjosé S, Saraiya M, Ferlay J, Bray F. Estimates of incidence and mortality of cervical cancer in 2018: a worldwide analysis. *Lancet Glob Health*. 2020 Feb;8(2):e191-e203. doi: 10.1016/S2214-109X(19)30482-6
- [2] Zampetakis LA, Melas C. The health belief model predicts vaccination intentions against COVID-19: A survey experiment approach. *Appl Psychol Health Well Being*. 2021 May;13(2):469-484. doi: 10.1111/aphw.12262
- [3] Haddison E, Tambasho A, Kouamen G, Ngwafor R. Vaccinators' Perception of HPV Vaccination in the Saa Health District of Cameroon. *Front Public*

Health. 2022 Jan 10;9:748910. doi: 10.3389/fpubh.2021.748910

[4] Brewer NT, Fazekas KI. Predictors of HPV vaccine acceptability: a theory-informed, systematic review. *Prev Med.* 2007 Aug-Sep;45(2-3):107-14. doi: 10.1016/j.ypmed.2007.05.013

[5] Hanley SJ, Yoshioka E, Ito Y, Konno R, Sasaki Y, Kishi R, Sakuragi N. An exploratory study of Japanese fathers' knowledge of and attitudes towards HPV and HPV vaccination: does marital status matter? *Asian Pac J Cancer Prev.* 2014;15(4):1837-43. doi: 10.7314/apjcp.2014.15.4.1837

[6] Rosenstock, Strecher, Becker. The Communication Initiative Network. 1994. Health Belief Model (Detailed). Available at: <https://www.comminit.com/content/health-belief-model-detailed>

[7] Marlow LA, Wardle J, Forster AS, Waller J. Ethnic differences in human papillomavirus awareness and vaccine acceptability. *J Epidemiol Community Health.* 2009 Dec;63(12):1010-5. doi: 10.1136/jech.2008.085886

[8] Dempsey AF, Zimet GD, Davis RL, Koutsky L. Factors that are associated with parental acceptance of human papillomavirus vaccines: a randomized intervention study of written information about HPV. *Pediatrics.* 2006 May;117(5):1486-93. doi: 10.1542/peds.2005-1381

[9] Watson-Jones D, Tomlin K, Remes P, Baisley K, Ponsiano R, Soteli S, de Sanjosé S, Chagalucha J, Kapiga S, Hayes RJ. Reasons for receiving or not

receiving HPV vaccination in primary schoolgirls in Tanzania: a case control study. *PLoS One.* 2012;7(10):e45231. doi: 10.1371/journal.pone.0045231

[10] Slomovitz BM, Sun CC, Frumovitz M, Soliman PT, Schmeler KM, Pearson HC, Berenson A, Ramirez PT, Lu KH, Bodurka DC. Are women ready for the HPV vaccine? *Gynecol Oncol.* 2006 Oct;103(1):151-4. doi: 10.1016/j.ygyno.2006.02.003

[11] Britt RK, Hatten KN, Chappuis SO. Perceived behavioral control, intention to get vaccinated, and usage of online information about the human papillomavirus vaccine. *Health Psychol Behav Med.* 2014 Jan 1;2(1):52-65. doi: 10.1080/21642850.2013.869175

[12] Gerend MA, Shepherd JE. Predicting human papillomavirus vaccine uptake in young adult women: comparing the health belief model and theory of planned behavior. *Ann Behav Med.* 2012 Oct;44(2):171-80. doi: 10.1007/s12160-012-9366-5

[13] Bennett KK, Buchanan JA, Adams AD. Social-cognitive predictors of intention to vaccinate against the human papillomavirus in college-age women. *J Soc Psychol.* 2012 Jul-Aug;152(4):480-92. doi: 10.1080/00224545.2011.639408

[14] Krawczyk AL, Perez S, Lau E, Holcroft CA, Amsel R, Knäuper B, Rosberger Z. Human papillomavirus vaccination intentions and uptake in college women. *Health Psychol.* 2012 Sep;31(5):685-93. doi: 10.1037/a002701.

